

The Influence of Social Media Marketing to Visit Intention through Brand Equity in Jatim Park 3

Dimas Eka Pratama¹, Nazief Nirwanto², Achmad Firdiansjah³

¹Post Graduate, University of Merdeka Malang, Malang, Indonesia

^{2,3}Lecturer, University of Merdeka Malang, Malang, Indonesia

Email address: dimasekapratama.xyz@gmail.com

Abstract— The purpose of this study to examine the influence of social media marketing to visit intention through brand equity in Jatim Park 3, Batu City. The design of this study design causality with quantitative approach. Sample of 200 members Jatim Park 3 FansPage on Facebook using an analysis tool Path. Data collection instrument Likert scale questionnaire. Results of the analysis showed that social media marketing is positive and significant effect on the interest been through brand equity.

Keywords— Social media marketing, visit intention, brand equity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Internet is part of the development of information technology that has been used for human life until today. In the era of the Internet allows people to send and receive unlimited amount of information from and to as much as humans. Contribution of the Internet in the context of a global economy including the adoption of the Internet as a medium of marketing communications.

Visit intention should be an important concern by marketers, given the buying interest is a process end in a purchase decision. The process of buying interest starting from the rise of demand for a product, and then forwarded to the processing of information by the consumer.

Social media enabling consumers to communicate with the company. Consumers are now able to conduct discussions, give their opinions and share their experiences with specific brands using social media. With the advent of social media, companies are now able to reach consumers with two-way communication (Kotler and Armstrong, 2012).

Companies that do social media marketing has provided an opportunity for consumers to interact better with company. Interaction is done by companies and consumers in the cost-effectiveness of social media has to increase brand awareness, brand image, and brand loyalty.

Promotional activities through social media companies can increase interest in visiting. Consumers interested in getting involved and provide input to the brand through social media where it can increase purchase intent. (Yi and Dahnil, 2014).

Fundamental to the prospect and promising potential in Jatim Park 3 on the side of growth as one of the tourist attractions in Batu City, the latest academic studies and research needs to be done to enrich knowledge in various perspectives. The interesting thing is how the assessment of consumers on social media marketing is done by Jatim Park 3 via social media accounts Facebook and Instagram managed companies as measured by the dimensions of social media

marketing has been determined. In terms of interest to visit, you need to know whether consumers are interested in discussing Jatim Park 3. Furthermore, the value of social media marketing as well as the level of consumer interest in discussing Jatim Park 3 is associated with the brand equity Jatim Park 3.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Visit Intention

Visit intention is consumer behavior that emerged in response to objects that show the desire of consumers to make a purchase (Kotler and Keller, 2012). In general, consumers make purchases by buying products that are already known, but will there are two other factors that arise between buying interest and purchase decisions. First, the influence of others. Second, unexpected situational factors. Thus, buying interest is not always culminate in the selection of the actual purchase (Kotler and Armstrong, 2012).

1. Indicators Interests Buy

Sciffman and Kanuk (2010) said that there are five indicators of buying interest, namely:

1.1 Considering buying

Consumers who have been looking for and learn information about products and services desired, then the consumer will evaluate the options and consider the purchase of the product.

1.2 Keen to try

Consumers who have been searching for information related to the desired product will determine the choice of product through the benefits or solutions offered products. The determination of this selection process is considered as cognitive-oriented. Consumers can assess a conscious and rational product to be interested in trying.

1.3 Want to know the product

Consumers who have tried the product, then consumers will have the desires to know the product. Consumers will regard the product as a set of attributes and features that vary in delivering the benefits are used to satisfy the needs.

1.4 Want to have a product

Consumers will take a position on a product by product evaluation and purchase intention form by choosing the preferred product.

Social Media Marketing

Social media marketing is a new form of interaction between "consumer to consumer" and "business to consumer"

which has an influence on the marketing communication process (Kotler and Armstrong, 2012). Social media marketing is a form of word of mouth (WOM) conducted online (Erdogmus and Cicek, 2012).

In his research, Erdogmus and Cicek (2012) reflect social media marketing through five dimensions:

1.1 Advantageous Campaign

Advantageous campaign is an activity designed to promote a product, service, or business. In conducting marketing campaigns need to plan an appropriate medium for disseminating information to the public. One of them using social media in the marketing campaign. The campaign is necessary to provide useful information to consumers so that consumers will be able to respond positively to the campaign conducted by the company.

1.2 Relevant Content

Relevant content needed by the company to do social media marketing, relevant content in question is to create a content that is relevant to the business lines that run. By having relevant content, the company will have a value in the conversation with the consumer and be able to position the brand as the proposer of consumers.

1.3 Frequently Update

Updates routinely content company needs to do to succeed in a brand do social media marketing. Companies that regularly updates the content in social media is having a good interaction to consumers.

1.4 Popular Content

Popular content will have a good reach and engagement for a company. Popular content will make social media users love of words or ideas presented by the company.

1.5 Various Platform and Application

A large selection of social media platforms become impossible engage with consumers, his company can analyze the target consumer brand and decided to participate in the most effective platform to communicate with consumers

Brand Equity

Brand equity is a value that allows a brand to get the strength, durability, and excellence that distinguishes the brand competitors (Kotler and Keller, 2009). Brand equity as a power which lies in what has been seen, heard, studied, thought and perceived by consumers to be a brand. (Kotler and Keller, 2009).

1.1 Brand Awareness

Brand awareness is the ability for consumers to recognize or remember that a brand is a member of a particular product category (Tjiptono, 2005). Brand awareness as a potential customer's ability to remember the brand was re sbagai a part of a particular product category (Kartajaya, 2010)

1.2 Brand Image

Brand Image (Brand image) is an emerging perception in the minds of consumers when considering a particular brand of product. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2008), the brand is a name, term, sign, symbol or design, or a combination of all these that show the identity of the products or services of one seller or group of sellers and differentiate the product from competitors' products.

1.3 Brand Loyalty

Brand loyalty is as a measure of the customer relationship to a brand (Tjiptono, 2005). Brand loyalty is the consumer preferences consistently to re-purchase the same brand in a specific product or a specific service category (Sciffman and Kanuk, 2004). Brand loyalty is strongly influenced by satisfaction or dissatisfaction with a brand that has accumulated in a certain period, as the impression of the quality of the product.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design Concept

This research uses a quantitative approach with the type of research used is explanatory research. The type of data used is quantitative data, which is the result of filling out the respondent's questionnaire. The population in this study is the followers of social media Jatim Park 3 on Facebook, amounting to 1680 followers (last accessed June 1, 2018). Samples were taken using the nonprobability sampling method. Population based on the calculation of 1680 people, the results of the calculation of 323 respondents the number of samples that became too many respondents, because of limited time, energy and cost, researchers only took 200 respondents. Researchers determined 200 respondents from Jatim Park 3 followers on Facebook. This research focuses on the study of marketing communications in the tourism industry, specifically those related to social media marketing and the variables that affect brand equity and visiting interests.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validity Test

The results of the validity test in this study were used to measure the level of accuracy of indicators assessing variables. Validity measurement by comparing the correlation value of each indicator on the statement item. the results of testing the validity of the 20 statements tested with the calculated coefficient r value greater than r table and the probability value is smaller than $\alpha = 5\%$. Thus, there is a significant relationship between the scores of each indicator with a significant correlation score, it can be said that the instruments used are valid, so that they can be used appropriately to measure the variables of social media marketing, brand equity, and visit intention.

Reliability Test

Reliability test results of this research are used to determine the extent to which the results of a measurement can be trusted. Questionnaires were used to collect reliable data, in this study using Cronbach alpha reliability models. Each coefficient greater than 0.6, so it can be concluded that the instrument used has high chances and answered consistently by respondents.

Classic Assumption Test

Normality Test

Normality test in this study is used to determine whether residuals are normally distributed or not.

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		X1_tot
N		200
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	28.57
	Std. Deviation	3.573
	Absolute	.068
Most Extreme Differences	Positive	.068
	Negative	-.062
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.967
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.307

a. Test distribution is Normal.
b. Calculated from data.

Fig. 1: data of normality test Kologrov-Smirnov

From the calculation results obtained sig. of 0.307 or greater than 0.05. The results of this research to meet the assumptions of normality

Multicollinearity Test

Multicollinearity test in this study is used to find out that there is no very strong relationship or no perfect linear relationship or between independent variables are not interrelated.

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
X	1.000	1.000
Y1	1.000	1.000

Fig. 2: Multicollinearity test results

Based on the results of the VIF calculation, it can be seen that social media marketing and brand equity variables have a VIF value of <5, thus the assumption test of the absence of multicollinearity can be fulfilled.

Heteroskedastisity test

At the scatterplot graph can be viewed dots spread randomly, do not form a particular pattern is clear, and spread both above and below the number 0 on the axis Y. Thus, it does not happen heteroskedastisity in this study.

Fig. 3: Heteroskedastisity test results

Path Analysis

The test model described in the previous section, then performed the track reconstruction causal relationships between variables with each other. The construction of paths obtained from the results of the analysis are as follows:

Fig. 4: Path Analysis

In figure it can be seen direct and indirect effects of each variable on purchase intention. Furthermore, to compare the direct and indirect influence of the existing path by diverting the path coefficients msaing formed in each lane, the highest multiplication value is the best path that can be used, while the amount of direct and indirect influence can be calculated as follows:

1.1 The direct effect of social media marketing (X) to purchase intention with $py2x$ path coefficient = 0,531X

1.2 The indirect effect of social media marketing (X) purchase intention (Y2) through brand equity (Y1) denan $py1x \times py2y1$ path coefficient = 0.486 x 0.385 = 0.187

Based on the test of direct and indirect influence on Table 1 it can be seen that social media marketing (X) directly influence the purchase intention (Y2) with a beta coefficient of 0.538. While the indirect influence of social media marketing (X) directly influence the purchase intention (Y2) through brand equity is equal to 0.187. With social media marketing has a direct influence of larger ones to purchase intention than the indirect effect is through the formation of brand equity. The results of analysis showed that social media marketing is positive and significant effect on the interest been through brand equity.

Variables	Direct Impact		Indirect Influence
	Y1	Y2	
X	0.486	.538	0.187
Y1		0.385	

Fig. 5: Effect of direct and indirect results

Discussion of results

Influence of Social Media Marketing to Brand Equity

The results show that social media marketing in the enterprise Java Park 3 turns as the variable positive and significant impact on brand equity, meaning that the higher the social media marketing in Java Park 3 will cause the higher the brand equity. The results support previous research

conducted Seo and Park (2017) that social media marketing relationships affect brand equity. In addition it also supports Balakrishnan study stating the effect of social media marketing on the purchase intention and brand loyalty, which is one element of brand equity.

The creation of brand equity as the power level of a brand in the minds of consumers will depend on the management of marketing communications, one of which came from the company's marketing activities in social media. The higher the value of social media marketing, the higher the tehradap consumer perceptions of a brand.

Effect of Brand Equity to Purchase Intention

Brand Equity effect on purchase intention, which means that an increase in brand equity can boost buying interest. Brand equity is built Jatim Park 3 with brand awareness, brand image and brand loyalty, where the consumer will perceive Jatim Park 3 is known as a tourist and educational influence on interest in visiting the beginning with awareness, consumers will easily remember Jatim Park 3 so willing to follow Jatim Park 3 on social media to receive information related to new attractions and promotional information that informed the Jatim Park 3 social media and would like to visit. Consumers who have been interested in visiting Jatim Park 3 will give a recommendation and refer Jatim Park 3 and then are interested in visiting Jatim Park 3. As Schiffman opinion and Kanuk (2000), buying interest shows that consumers will follow the experiences, preferences, and the external environment to gather information, evaluate alternatives, and make decisions. The results are consistent with Chen and Chang (2008) and Gunawardane (2015) which states that the brand equity influence the buying interest.

The influence of social media marketing on the purchase intention

Social media marketing effect on purchase intention, which means that the increase in social media marketing can boost buying interest. Social media marketing is built Jatim Park 3 with advantegeous campaign, relevant content, frequently update is content, popular content show that Java Park 3 has conducted activities marketing activities through social media by giving a campaign that is useful, making content that is relevant to the lines of business, and do perbaharuan of the content created and would like to visit. Consumers who have been interested in visiting Jatim Park 3 will give a recommendation and refer Jatim Park 3 and then are interested in visiting Jatim Park 3.

The influence of social media marketing on the purchase intention through brand equity

Social media marketing Jatim Park 3 have relevant content to provide appropriate information dengan Jatim Park 3 business lines in the field of education and travel and can create involvement on each post, causing the interaction between consumers and companies. Through brand equity as mediation menamkan brand awareness, brand image and brand loyalty of existing customers that Jatim Park where tourism and education have many options rides and consumers are expected to inform and recommend Jatim Park 3 others can affect the buying interest in interest, desire, and conviction reflected consumers will find information and learn about the

attractions offered by the Jatim Park 3 so interested and willing to visit Jatim Park 3.

Brand equity mediate the effect of social media marketing to the buying interest, this suggests social media marketing program that the company can increase the interest to visit, if supported with brand equity.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research and data analysis on the conclusions of this study are:

- A. Brand Equity's main contribution is the brand image that is reflected from a perception that comes to the minds of consumers when considering a particular brand of product. Interests been formed from the interest, desire, and conviction. The main contribution is the interest the interest been reflected in the sensitivity of consumers to the product, in this stage of consumer generated and created an interest in the product.
- B. *Social media marketing* formed of advantageous campaign, relevant content, content is frequently updated, popular content affect brand equity which is formed of brand awareness, brand image and brand loyalty in Java Park 3.
- C. Established brand equity of brand awareness, brand image and brand loyalty in Java Park 3, in this case the brand image, as Jatim Park 3 is known as educational menawakan tourist attractions of interest to visit influential quality.
- D. *Social media marketing* in this case the relevant content of the information provided reflected social media Jatim Park 3 in accordance with the line of business engaged in tourism and unknown to many people able to affect the interest of consumers to consider for a visit, for the next willing to visit Jatim Park 3.
- E. Brand equity in this case the brand image, namely Java Park 3 is known as a place of educational tours that menawakan attractions of a quality that has been formed in the minds of consumers, mediates the influence of Social media marketing that promotes relevant content that is social media Jatim Park 3 is able to provide information in accordance with the line of business in the field of tourism and creating engagement in the form of likes, comments, and share it affects the interest to visit.

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